

Smarandache idempotents in certain types of group rings

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Abstract:

In this paper we study S-idempotents of the group ring \mathbb{Z}_2G where G is a finite cyclic group of order n . We give a condition on n such that every nonzero idempotent element of the group ring \mathbb{Z}_2G is Smarandache idempotent and we find Smarandache idempotents of the group ring $\mathcal{K}G$, where \mathcal{K} is an algebraically closed field of characteristic 0 and G is a finite cyclic group.

Keywords: Idempotent, S-idempotent, group ring, algebraically closed field.

Introduction:

Smarandache idempotent element in rings introduced by Vasantha Kandasamy [1]. A Smarandache idempotent (S-idempotent) of the ring \mathcal{R} is an element $0 \neq x \in \mathcal{R}$ such that

- 1) $x^2 = x$
- 2) There exists $a \in \mathcal{R} \setminus \{0, 1, x\}$
 - i) $a^2 = x$ and
 - ii) $xa = a$ ($ax = a$) or $ax = x$ ($xa = x$).

She introduced many Smarandache concepts [2]. Vasantha Kandasamy and Moon K. Chetry discuss S-idempotents in some type of group rings [3]. A prime number p of the form $p = 2^k - 1$ where k is a prime number called Mersenne prime [4]. In section one of this paper we study S-idempotents of the group ring \mathbb{Z}_2G where G is a finite cyclic group of order n . If $n = 2p$, p is a Mersenne prime, we show that every nonzero idempotent element is S-

idempotent and we find the number of S-idempotent element. In section two we study S-idempotents of the group ring $\mathcal{K}G$ where \mathcal{K} is an algebraically closed field of characteristic 0 and G is a finite cyclic group, we show that every non trivial idempotent is S-idempotent.

1. S-idempotents of \mathbb{Z}_2G

In this section we study S-idempotents in the group ring \mathbb{Z}_2G where G is a finite cyclic group of order n , specially where $n=2p$, p is a Mersenne prime (i.e. $p = 2^k - 1$ for some prime k).

Theorem 1.1.

The group ring \mathbb{Z}_2G where $G = \langle g \mid g^m = 1 \rangle$ is a cyclic group of an odd order $m > 1$, has at least two non trivial idempotent elements, moreover no non trivial idempotent element is S-idempotent.

Proof: Consider the element

$$\alpha = g + g^2 + g^3 + \dots + g^{\frac{m-1}{2}} + g^{\frac{m-1}{2}+1} + \dots$$

+ g^{m-1} , of \mathbb{Z}_2G . Since the coefficient of each g^i , $i = 1, \dots, m$ is in \mathbb{Z}_2 , $\alpha^2 = g^2 + g^4 + \dots + g^{m-1} + g + g^3 + \dots + g^{m-2}$. Hence $\alpha^2 = \alpha$, that is α is an idempotent element, so $(1 + \alpha)$ is also an idempotent element. It remains to show that no idempotent element of \mathbb{Z}_2G is an S-idempotent. Suppose

$$\alpha = a_1 + a_2g + a_3g^2 + \dots + a_{\frac{m-1}{2}+1}g^{\frac{m-1}{2}} + \dots + a_m g^{m-1},$$

is a non trivial S-idempotent. Thus α is different from 0 and 1, moreover there exists β in $\mathbb{Z}_2G \setminus \{0, 1, \alpha\}$ such that $\beta^2 = \alpha$, let $\beta = b_1 + b_2g + b_3g^2 + \dots + b_{\frac{m-1}{2}+1}g^{\frac{m-1}{2}} + \dots + b_m g^{m-1}$,

where $b_i \in \mathbb{Z}_2$. But $\alpha^2 = \alpha$, which means that

$$a_1 + a_2g^2 + a_3g^4 + \dots + a_{\frac{m-1}{2}+1}g^{m-1} + \dots + a_m g^{m-2} = b_1 + b_2g^2 + b_3g^4 + \dots + b_{\frac{m-1}{2}+1}g^{m-1} + \dots + b_m g^{m-2}.$$

It follows that $a_i = b_i$ for each $(1 \leq i \leq m)$. Therefore $\alpha = \beta$, which is an obvious contradiction.

The group ring \mathbb{Z}_2G , where G is acyclic group of an odd order may contains more than two idempotent elements as it is shown by the following example.

Example 1.1.

Consider the group ring \mathbb{Z}_2G where $G = \langle g \mid g^7 = 1 \rangle$ is a cyclic group of order 7. By Theorem 1.1, $g + g^2 + g^3 + g^4 + g^5 + g^6$ and $1 + g + g^2 + g^3 + g^4 + g^5 + g^6$ are

idempotent elements, In addition $(g + g^2 + g^4)^2 = g^2 + g^4 + g$ and $(1 + g + g^2 + g^4)^2 = 1 + g^2 + g^4 + g$, so $1 + g + g^2 + g^4$ and $g + g^2 + g^4$ are idempotent elements. Therefore \mathbb{Z}_2G has more than two idempotent elements.

The proof of the following result is not difficult.

Theorem 1.2.

If α is an S-idempotent of the group ring \mathbb{Z}_2G where G is a cyclic group of order n , then $(1 + \alpha)$ is an S-idempotent of \mathbb{Z}_2G .

Theorem 1.3.

The group ring \mathbb{Z}_2G , where $G = \langle g \mid g^{2n} = 1 \rangle$ is a cyclic group of order $2n$, n is an odd prime, has at least two S-idempotents.

Proof: Let $\alpha = g^2 + g^4 + \dots + g^{n-1} + g^{n+1} + \dots + g^{2n-2}$. Thus

$\alpha^2 = g^4 + g^8 + \dots + g^{2n-2} + g^2 + g^6 + \dots + g^{2n-4} = \alpha$. Hence α is an idempotent element, so $(1 + \alpha)$ is also an idempotent element. We will show that α is S-idempotent, so let

$$\beta = g + g^{n+2} + g^3 + g^{n+4} + \dots + g^{\frac{n-1}{2}} + g^{\frac{3n+1}{2}} + \dots + g^{n-2} + g^{2n-1}.$$

It is clear that $\beta^2 = \alpha$. We claim that $\alpha\beta = \beta$. For this purpose we describe the multiplication $\alpha\beta$ by the following array say \mathcal{A} :

$$\mathcal{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \boxed{g^3} & g^5 & \dots & g^{n-2} & g^n & g^{n+2} & \dots & g^{2n-3} & g^{2n-1} \\ \boxed{g^{n+4}} & g^{n+6} & \dots & g^{2n-1} & g^{2n+1} & g^{2n+3} & \dots & g^{n-2} & g^n \\ g^5 & g^7 & \dots & g^n & g^{n+2} & g^{n+4} & \dots & g^{2n-1} & \boxed{g} \\ g^{n+6} & g^{n+8} & \dots & g & g^3 & g^5 & \dots & g^n & \boxed{g^{n+2}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \boxed{g^{\frac{3n+1}{2}}} & g^{\frac{3n+5}{2}} & \dots & g^{\frac{5n-9}{2}} & g^{\frac{5n-5}{2}} & g^{\frac{5n-1}{2}} & \dots & g^{\frac{7n-11}{2}} & g^{\frac{7n-7}{2}} \\ \boxed{g^{\frac{n+3}{2}}} & g^{\frac{n+7}{2}} & \dots & g^{\frac{3n-7}{2}} & g^{\frac{3n-3}{2}} & g^{\frac{3n+1}{2}} & \dots & g^{\frac{5n-9}{2}} & g^{\frac{5n-5}{2}} \\ g^{\frac{3n+5}{2}} & g^{\frac{3n+9}{2}} & \dots & g^{\frac{5n-5}{2}} & g^{\frac{5n-1}{2}} & g^{\frac{5n+3}{2}} & \dots & g^{\frac{7n-7}{2}} & \boxed{g^{\frac{7n-3}{2}}} \\ g^{\frac{n+7}{2}} & g^{\frac{n+11}{2}} & \dots & g^{\frac{3n-3}{2}} & g^{\frac{3n+1}{2}} & g^{\frac{5n+3}{2}+1} & \dots & g^{\frac{5n-5}{2}} & \boxed{g^{\frac{5n-1}{2}}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \boxed{g^{n-2}} & g^n & \dots & g^{2n-7} & g^{2n-5} & g^{2n-3} & \dots & g^{n-8} & g^{n-6} \\ \boxed{g^{2n-1}} & g & \dots & g^{n-6} & g^{n-4} & g^{n-2} & \dots & g^{2n-7} & g^{2n-5} \\ g^n & g^{n+2} & \dots & g^{2n-5} & g^{2n-3} & g^{2n-1} & \dots & g^{n-6} & \boxed{g^{n-4}} \\ g & g^3 & \dots & g^{n-4} & g^{n-2} & g^n & \dots & g^{2n-5} & \boxed{g^{2n-3}} \\ g & g^3 & \dots & g^{p-4} & g^{p-2} & g^p & \dots & g^{2p-5} & \boxed{g^{2p-3}} \end{bmatrix}$$

That is $\mathcal{A} = [a_{ij}]_{(n-1) \times (n-1)}$, where a_{ij} is the summand of $\alpha\beta$ which is equal to the product of the i th summand of β with the j th summand of α . This means $\alpha\beta = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} a_{ij}$. If we take the first and the third rows of this array we will see that g^i occurs twice for each i except ($i = 1, 3$). By adding the terms of this two rows it remains only $g + g^3$ (observing that the coefficient of each g^i , $i=1, 2, \dots, m$ is in \mathbb{Z}_2). Again by adding the second and

the fourth rows in this array, according to the same argument it remains only $g^{p+2} + g^{p+4}$. Proceeding in this manner we will get the $(p-3)$ th and the $(p-1)$ th rows, and adding their terms it remains only $g^{2p-3} + g^{2p-1}$. Thus we get

$$\alpha\beta = g + g^{n+2} + g^3 + g^{n+4} + \dots + g^{\frac{n-1}{2}} + g^{\frac{3n+1}{2}} + \dots + g^{n-2} + g^{2n-1} = \beta.$$

Hence α is S-idempotent. By Theorem 1.2, $(1 + \alpha)$ is also S-idempotent. This complete the proof.

Lemma 1.4.

In \mathbb{Z}_2G , where $G = \langle g \mid g^{2^p} = 1 \rangle$, p is a Mersenne prime (i.e. $p = 2^k - 1$ for some prime k) $g^{2^l} = g^{2^{k+1}l}$ and the elements of $\mathcal{S} = \{g^{2^l}, g^{2^{2l}}, g^{2^{3l}}, \dots, g^{2^{k-1}l}, g^{2^{kl}}\}$ are distinct for each odd number l less than p . **Proof:** Since $2^{k+1}l - 2l = 2l(2^k - 1) = 2lp$, $2^{k+1}l \equiv 2l \pmod{2p}$, which implies that $g^{2^l} = g^{2^{k+1}l}$. Now suppose that $g^{2^l} = g^{2^{tl}}$ (for some $1 < t \leq k$). This means $2^{tl} \equiv 2l \pmod{2p}$, hence $(2^k - 1)l \mid (2^{t-1} - 1)l$ yields either $(2^k - 1) \mid l$ or $(2^k - 1) \mid (2^{t-1} - 1)$. But $(2^k - 1) \mid l$ contradicts the hypothesis that $l < p$, and if $(2^k - 1) \mid (2^{t-1} - 1)$, hence $k < t - 1$, contradiction with $1 < t \leq k$.

Lemma 1.5.

If $p = 2^k - 1$ is a Mersenne prime, then $k \mid (2^k - 2)$.

Proof: Since k is prime, according to Fermat's Little Theorem, $k \mid (2^k - 2)$.

Combining the last two lemmas we deduce that in the group ring \mathbb{Z}_2G , where G is a cyclic group generated by g of order $2p$, p is a Mersenne prime (i.e. $p = 2^k - 1$ for some prime k), if $m = \frac{2^k - 2}{k}$, then $\alpha = g^2 + g^4 + \dots + g^{p-1} + g^{p+1} + \dots + g^{2p-2}$, can be partitioned to sum of m elements say $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_m$ each α_i ($1 \leq i \leq m$) is of the form

$$\alpha_i = g^{2^l} + g^{2^{2l}} + \dots + g^{2^{k-1}l} + g^{2^{kl}},$$

where l is an odd number.

Theorem 1.6.

Let \mathbb{Z}_2G be a group ring, where $G = \langle g \mid g^{2^p} = 1 \rangle$ is a cyclic group of order $2p$, p is a Mersenne prime. Then every element of the form $\alpha = g^{2^l} + g^{2^{2l}} + \dots + g^{2^{kl}}$, is an S-idempotent (l is an odd number).

Proof: Let $\alpha = g^{2^l} + g^{2^{2l}} + \dots + g^{2^{kl}}$. By Lemma 1.4, all elements in $\mathcal{S} = \{g^{2^l}, g^{2^{2l}}, \dots, g^{2^{kl}}\}$ are distinct, moreover $g^{2^l} = g^{2^{k+1}l}$. Hence $\alpha^2 = \alpha$. Now, let $\beta = g^{t_1} + g^{t_2} + g^{t_3} + \dots + g^{t_k}$ and x_i , $i \geq 2$ be the smallest positive integer such that $x_i < 2p$. Thus $x_i \equiv 2^{i-1}l \pmod{2p}$, this means $x_i = 2^{i-1}l - 2pr$, for some $r \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Define t_i by

$$t_i = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} x_i & \text{if } \frac{1}{2} x_i \text{ is odd } (2 \leq i \leq k) \\ \frac{1}{2} x_i + p & \text{if } \frac{1}{2} x_i \text{ is even } (2 \leq i \leq k). \end{cases}$$

If $\frac{1}{2} x_i$ is odd, then $(g^{t_i})^2 = (g^{2^{i-1}l - pr})^2 = g^{2^i l}$. Hence $\beta^2 = \alpha$. If $\frac{1}{2} x_i$ is even, then $(g^{t_i})^2 = g^{2^i l}$, and $\beta^2 = \alpha$ for each $(2 \leq i \leq k)$. We will show that $\alpha\beta = \beta$. For this purpose as before we describe the multiplication $\alpha\beta$ in the following array say \mathcal{A} :

$$\mathcal{A} = \begin{bmatrix} g^{3l} & g^{5l} & g^{9l} & \dots & g^{l(2^{k-2}+1)} & g^{l(2^{k-1}+1)} & \boxed{g^{l(2^k+1)}} \\ \boxed{g^{t_2+2l}} & g^{t_2+4l} & g^{t_2+8l} & \dots & g^{t_2+2^{k-2}l} & g^{t_2+2^{k-1}l} & g^{t_2+2^k l} \\ g^{t_3+2l} & \boxed{g^{t_3+4l}} & g^{t_3+8l} & \dots & g^{t_3+2^{k-2}l} & g^{t_3+2^{k-1}l} & g^{t_3+2^k l} \\ g^{t_4+2l} & g^{t_4+4l} & \boxed{g^{t_4+8l}} & \dots & g^{t_4+2^{k-2}l} & g^{t_4+2^{k-1}l} & g^{t_4+2^k l} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ g^{t_{k-1}+2l} & g^{t_{k-1}+4l} & g^{t_{k-1}+8l} & \dots & \boxed{g^{t_{k-1}+2^{k-2}l}} & g^{t_{k-1}+2^{k-1}l} & g^{t_{k-1}+2^k l} \\ g^{t_k+2l} & g^{t_k+4l} & g^{t_k+8l} & \dots & g^{t_k+2^{k-2}l} & \boxed{g^{t_k+2^{k-1}l}} & g^{t_k+2^k l} \end{bmatrix} = [a_{ij}]_{k \times k},$$

where a_{ij} is the summand of $\alpha\beta$ which is equal to the product of the i th summand of β with j th summand of α . This means $\alpha\beta = \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^k a_{ij}$. We complete the proof by the following three steps.

Step 1: Considering the first and the k th column in this array we claim that

$$a_{1j} = a_{(j+1)k} \quad \dots(1),$$

for each $(1 \leq j \leq k-1)$, equivalently

$$g^{(2^j+1)l} = g^{t_{j+1}+2^k l}.$$

Let $\omega = t_{j+1} + 2^k l - (2^j + 1)l$. Now, $x_{j+1} \equiv 2^{j+1}l \pmod{2p}$, thus $x_{j+1} = 2^{j+1}l - 2pr$, for some $r \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. If $\frac{1}{2}x_{j+1}$ is odd, then $\frac{1}{2}x_{j+1} = 2^j l - pr$ is odd (this hold only if r is odd), hence $t_{j+1} = 2^j l - pr$. So, $\omega = 2^j l - pr + 2^k l - 2^j l - l \equiv 0 \pmod{2p}$. Therefore $(2^j + 1)l \equiv t_{j+1} + 2^k l \pmod{2p}$. This yields (1). If $\frac{1}{2}x_{j+1}$ is even, then $\frac{1}{2}x_{j+1} = 2^j l - pr$ is even (this hold only if r is even), hence $t_{j+1} = 2^j l - pr + p$. So, $\omega = (1-r)p + lp \equiv 0 \pmod{2p}$. Hence $(2^j + 1)l \equiv t_{j+1} + 2^k l \pmod{2p}$. This also yields (1). This implies that $a_{1j} + a_{(j+1)k} = 0 \pmod{2p}$,

therefore by adding the terms of the first row and the k th column it remains only $a_{1k} = g^{l(2^k+1)}$.

Step 2: Consider the subarray $B = (b_{ij})_{(k-1) \times (k-1)}$ of $\mathcal{A} = (a_{ij})_{k \times k}$, where $b_{ij} = a_{(i+1)j}$ for each $(1 \leq i, j \leq k-1)$, by neglecting the first row and the k th column, we will show that

$$b_{ij} = b_{ji} \quad \dots(2),$$

for all $(1 \leq i, j \leq k-1)$ such that $(i \neq j)$, equivalently $g^{t_{(i+1)}+2^j l} = g^{t_{(j+1)}+2^i l}$. Let $\omega = t_{i+1} + 2^j l - t_{j+1} - 2^i l$. Now, $x_{i+1} = 2^{i+1}l - 2pr$ and $x_{j+1} = 2^{j+1}l - 2ps$, for some $r, s \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Thus $\frac{1}{2}x_{i+1} = 2^i l - pr$ and $\frac{1}{2}x_{j+1} = 2^j l - ps$. If $\frac{1}{2}x_{i+1}$ and $\frac{1}{2}x_{j+1}$ are even, hence $2^i l - pr$ and $2^j l - ps$ are even (this hold only if r and s are even), it follows $t_{i+1} = 2^i l - pr + p$ and $t_{j+1} = 2^j l - ps + p$. So, $\omega = (s-r)p \equiv 0 \pmod{2p}$. Hence $t_{i+1} + 2^j l \equiv t_{j+1} + 2^i l \pmod{2p}$. This yields (2). If $\frac{1}{2}x_{i+1}$ and $\frac{1}{2}x_{j+1}$ are odd, it is clearly $\omega = (s-r)p \equiv 0 \pmod{2p}$. Hence $t_{i+1} + 2^j l \equiv t_{j+1} + 2^i l \pmod{2p}$.

This also establishes (2). If $\frac{1}{2} x_{i+1}$ is odd and $\frac{1}{2} x_{j+1}$ is even, it is also clear that $\omega=(s-r-1)p \equiv 0 \pmod{2p}$. Thus $t_{i+1} + 2^i l \equiv t_{j+1} + 2^i l \pmod{2p}$. This also yields (2). If $\frac{1}{2} x_{i+1}$ is even and $\frac{1}{2} x_{j+1}$ is odd, thus by using similar argument we get $t_{i+1} + 2^i l \equiv t_{j+1} + 2^i l \pmod{2p}$. This also yields (2). For all cases we get $b_{ij} + b_{ji} = 0 \ (1 \leq i, j \leq k-1)$.

Step 3: From Step 1 and Step 2 we get that $\alpha\beta = a_{1k} + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} b_{ii}$ and it is not difficult to show that $\alpha\beta = \beta$ which means that α is an S-idempotent.

We call an S-idempotent of \mathbb{Z}_2G of the form $\alpha = g^{2l} + g^{2^2l} + \dots + g^{2^{kl}}$, where l is an odd number a basic S-idempotent.

Example 1.2.

Consider the group ring \mathbb{Z}_2G where $G = \langle g \mid g^{62} = 1 \rangle$ is a cyclic group of order 62 (i.e. $p=31$ and $k=5$). By Theorem 1.7, if $l=1$, then $\alpha = g^2 + g^4 + g^8 + g^{16} + g^{32}$ and $\beta = g + g^{33} + g^{35} + g^{39} + g^{47}$. It is clear that $\beta^2 = \alpha$. Let us describe the multiplication $\alpha\beta$ by the following array say \mathcal{A} :

$$\mathcal{A} = \begin{bmatrix} g^3 & g^5 & g^9 & g^{17} & g^{33} \\ g^{35} & g^{37} & g^{41} & g^{49} & g^3 \\ g^{37} & g^{39} & g^{43} & g^{51} & g^5 \\ g^{41} & g^{43} & g^{47} & g^{55} & g^9 \\ g^{49} & g^{51} & g^{55} & g & g^{17} \end{bmatrix}$$

Hence applying Theorem 1.6, we get $\alpha\beta = g + g^{33} + g^{35} + g^{39} + g^{47} = \beta$.

Theorem 1.7.

If α_1 and α_2 are two basic S-

idempotents in \mathbb{Z}_2G , where G is a cyclic group of order $2p$, p a Mersenne prime, then $\alpha_1 + \alpha_2$ is S-idempotent.

Proof: Let α_1, α_2 be two distinct basic S-idempotents in \mathbb{Z}_2G , so there exist β_1 and β_2 such that $\beta_1^2 = \alpha_1, \alpha_1\beta_1 = \beta_1, \beta_2^2 = \alpha_2$ and $\alpha_2\beta_2 = \beta_2$.

Now, $(\beta_1 + \beta_2)^2 = \beta_1^2 + \beta_2^2 = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2$, and $(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)(\beta_1 + \beta_2) = \alpha_1\beta_1 + \alpha_1\beta_2 + \alpha_2\beta_1 + \alpha_2\beta_2 = \beta_1 + \beta_2 + \alpha_1\beta_2 + \alpha_2\beta_1$.

We show that $\alpha_1\beta_2 + \alpha_2\beta_1 = 0$. By describing the multiplications $\alpha_1\beta_2$ and $\alpha_2\beta_1$ by the two arrays \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} respectively and using similar argument of Theorem 1.6, we get $\mathcal{A} + \mathcal{B} = 0$ that is $\alpha_1\beta_2 + \alpha_2\beta_1 = 0$. Therefore $\alpha_1 + \alpha_2$ is an S-idempotent.

Theorem 1.8.

If $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n$ are n basic S-idempotents in \mathbb{Z}_2G where G is a cyclic group of order $2p$, p is a Mersenne prime, then $\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \dots + \alpha_n$ is S-idempotent.

Proof: Follows from Theorem 1.7.

By combining all previous results concerning the group ring \mathbb{Z}_2G , where G is a cyclic group of order $2p$, p is a Mersenne prime we get the following result

Theorem 1.9.

Consider the group ring \mathbb{Z}_2G where G is a cyclic group of order $2p$, p is a Mersenne prime. Then

- 1) Every non trivial idempotent is S-idempotent.
- 2) The number of non trivial S-idempotents is $2(2^m - 1)$, where $m = \frac{p-1}{k}$.

Proof: 1) Follows from Theorems 1.6, 1.7, 1.8 and Theorem 1.2.

2) From Theorems 1.6, 1.7, and 1.8, by using the concepts of probability theory we conclude that the number of S-idempotent in \mathbb{Z}_2G is

$$\lambda = 2 \left(\binom{m}{1} + \binom{m}{2} + \dots + \binom{m}{m} \right) = 2(2^m - 1), \text{ where } m = \frac{p-1}{k}.$$

2. S-idempotents in the group ring of a finite cyclic group over a field of characteristic zero

In this section, we study the group ring $\mathcal{K}G$ where \mathcal{K} is an algebraically closed field of characteristic 0 and G is a finite cyclic group of order n . We get that every nontrivial idempotent element in this group ring $\mathcal{K}G$ is an S-idempotent element.

Theorem 2.1.

Let \mathcal{K} be algebraically closed field of characteristic 0 and G is a finite cyclic group of order n . Then every nontrivial idempotent element in $\mathcal{K}G$ is an S-idempotent.

Proof: By [5], $\mathcal{K}G$ has $2^n - 2$ nontrivial

idempotent elements, let $\alpha = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} r_i g^i \in \mathcal{K}G$ be an idempotent element.

Put $\beta = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-r_i)g^i \in \mathcal{K}G$. Hence

$$\beta^2 = \left(\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-r_i)g^i \right)^2 = \left((-1) \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} r_i g^i \right)^2 = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} r_i g^i = \alpha$$

$$\text{Now, } \alpha\beta = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} r_i g^i \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-r_i)g^i = (-1) \left(\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} r_i g^i \right)^2 = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-r_i)g^i = \beta.$$

Therefore every nontrivial idempotent in $\mathcal{K}G$ is an S-idempotent.

Recall that β called Smarandache Co-idempotent of α [1]. The following example shows that the Smarandache co-idempotent need not be unique in general.

Example 2.1.

Let G be a cyclic group of order 3, and \mathcal{K} is an algebraically closed field of characteristic 0, and let $\alpha = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} r_i g^i \in \mathcal{K}G$. If α is an idempotent element, then by [5], the values of r_0, r_1 and r_2 are followings

r_0	0	$\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	1
r_1	0	$\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{-1 + \sqrt{3}i}{6}$	$\frac{-1 + \sqrt{3}i}{6}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{-1 + \sqrt{3}i}{6}$	$\frac{-1 + \sqrt{3}i}{6}$	0
r_2	0	$\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{-1 + \sqrt{3}i}{6}$	$\frac{-1 + \sqrt{3}i}{6}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	$\frac{-1 + \sqrt{3}i}{6}$	$\frac{-1 + \sqrt{3}i}{6}$	0

Consider the S-idempotents,

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{2}{3} - \frac{1}{3}g - \frac{1}{3}g^2, \quad \alpha_2 = \frac{2}{3} + \frac{1 + \sqrt{3}i}{6}g + \frac{1 - \sqrt{3}i}{6}g^2 \text{ and } \alpha_3 = \frac{2}{3} + \frac{1 - \sqrt{3}i}{6}g + \frac{1 + \sqrt{3}i}{6}g^2.$$

For each $(1 \leq i \leq 3)$, α_i has three Co-idempotents we denote them by β_{ij} $(1 \leq j \leq 3)$. They are $\beta_{11} = \frac{-2}{3} + \frac{1}{3}g + \frac{1}{3}g^2$,

$$\beta_{12} = \frac{\sqrt{3}i}{3}g - \frac{\sqrt{3}i}{3}g^2, \quad \beta_{13} = \frac{-\sqrt{3}i}{3} + \frac{\sqrt{3}i}{3}g,$$

$$\beta_{21} = \frac{-2}{3} - \frac{1 - \sqrt{3}i}{6}g + \frac{-1 + \sqrt{3}i}{6}g^2,$$

$$\beta_{22} = \frac{-3 + \sqrt{3}i}{6}g + \frac{-3 - \sqrt{3}i}{6}g^2, \quad \beta_{23} = \frac{3 - \sqrt{3}i}{6}g + \frac{1 + \sqrt{3}i}{6}g^2, \quad \beta_{31} = \frac{-2}{3} - \frac{1 - \sqrt{3}i}{6}g - \frac{1 + \sqrt{3}i}{6}g^2,$$

$$\beta_{32} = \frac{-3 - \sqrt{3}i}{6}g + \frac{3 + \sqrt{3}i}{6}g^2, \quad \beta_{33} = \frac{3 + \sqrt{3}i}{6}g + \frac{-3 - \sqrt{3}i}{6}g^2, \text{ respectively. We see that}$$

$\alpha_1\beta_{1j} = \beta_{1j}$, $\alpha_2\beta_{2j} = \beta_{2j}$ and $\alpha_3\beta_{3j} = \beta_{3j}$, $\beta_{1j}^2 = \alpha_1$, $\beta_{2j}^2 = \alpha_2$ and $\beta_{3j}^2 = \alpha_3$, for each $(1 \leq i \leq 3)$.

Theorem 2.2.

Let \mathcal{K} be an algebraically closed field of characteristic 0 and $G = \mathbb{Z}_m \times \mathbb{Z}_n$. Then every nontrivial idempotent element in $\mathcal{K}G$ is an S-idempotent.

Proof: If m, n are relatively prime, then the proof is given in Theorem 2.1, since $\mathbb{Z}_m \times \mathbb{Z}_n \cong \mathbb{Z}_{mn}$ is cyclic. If m and n are not relatively prime, for each $(k, j) \in G$ let $(k, j) = g_{kn+j}$ ($0 \leq k \leq m-1, 0 \leq j \leq n-1$), and let

$\alpha = \sum_{i=0}^{mn-1} r_i g_i \in \mathcal{K}G$ be an idempotent element [6]. Take $\beta = \sum_{i=0}^{mn-1} (-r_i) g_i \in \mathcal{K}G$, then it is clear that

$$\beta^2 = \alpha \text{ and } \alpha\beta = \beta.$$

Therefore every idempotent element in $\mathcal{K}G$ is an S-idempotent.

Finally we concern the group ring $\mathcal{R}G$ where \mathcal{R} is an integral domain and G is a finite group of order n . We give a condition under which $\mathcal{R}G$ contains S-idempotents.

Theorem 2.3.

Let \mathcal{R} be an integral domain, and let

G be a finite group of order n . If some prime divisor p of n is a unit in \mathcal{R} and

- 1) $p^3 = p^{-1}$ or
- 2) $p = p^{-1}$ or
- 3) $p = 2$.

Then the group ring $\mathcal{R}G$ has S-idempotent.

Proof: 1) Since p is a prime dividing n , and p is a unit in \mathcal{R} then by [7] $\alpha = p^{-1} \sum_{x \in H} x$ is a nontrivial idempotent where H is a subgroup of G of order p . Let $\beta = p \sum_{x \in H} x$. Then $\alpha\beta = p^{-1} p \sum_{x \in H} x \sum_{x \in H} x = p \sum_{x \in H} x = \beta$, and $\beta^2 = p^2 (\sum_{x \in H} x)^2 = p^3 \sum_{x \in H} x = p^{-1} \sum_{x \in H} x = \alpha$.

Hence α is a S-idempotent.

2) we have $\alpha = p^{-1} \sum_{x \in H} x$ is a nontrivial idempotent. Let $\beta = \sum_{x \in H} x$. Then

$$\alpha\beta = p^{-1} \sum_{x \in H} x \sum_{x \in H} x = \sum_{x \in H} x = \beta, \text{ and } \beta^2 = (\sum_{x \in H} x)^2 = p \sum_{x \in H} x = p^{-1} \sum_{x \in H} x = \alpha.$$

Therefore α is a S-idempotent.

3) Since $p = 2$ divides n , then $|G| = 2k$ and $\alpha = 2^{-1}(1 + g^k)$. Let $\beta = (1 + g^k) - \alpha$. Then it is clear that $\beta^2 = \alpha$ and $\alpha\beta = \beta$. So α is an S-idempotent.

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